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LUSTYCH Jarek

*visual/audio/multimedia artist working
with non-human co-agents in rivers,
mushrooms, and material systems.*

Foreign Objekt 2022–2025 Research

Resident

FACING THE HORROR OF THE UNIVERSE

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Abstract

This article argues in favor of attributing the post-humanistic turn to the horror of the abyss which people experienced upon seeing a picture of the Earth taken from the Moon. This dramatic shift in perspective made us look at ourselves as passengers of a spaceship racing through the void. Faced with this extreme loneliness, man finds relief in the sense of connection with all earthly beings. The first part of the essay explores the differences between ontological dualism, the division into the intentional worlds of human subjects and the objective world of material things, and the unifying Agent Network Theory (ANT).

Abandoning the former patterns of superficial artistic attitudes that continued human expansion, the article postulates the interaction of human and non-human entities as ethical and more creatively promising. A particular concern has been to shift the weight of emphasis both conceptually and methodologically away from anthropocentric vision. The author applies agency theory to introduce a figure of symbiotic authorship and its surrounding subordinate elements - especially those that can be used to meet the needs of agency development. The purpose of the second part of the paper is to present an approach for exploring the immanent traits of beings as expressions of life and to propose possible models of artistic collaboration between genres. The introduced research, whose results are manifold, can be applied to specific domains and contexts. In presenting these possibilities, a symbiotic artist may offer a comprehensive standpoint to reflect upon potential futures.

The most important work of 20th-century art is a photo of the Earth as seen from the moon. This dramatic shift in perspective made us look at ourselves as passengers of a spaceship racing through the void, or as inhabitants of a grain of sand suspended in the abyss. We felt how strong our relationship was with the place where we live and with which we share our fate. When faced with the horror of the abyss, man, like a spectator of a Greek tragedy, finds relief in the sense of connection with all beings on Earth. Perhaps it is no coincidence that at about the same time, as photographs of the Earth as seen from outer space became available, Land Art appears. And although some artists from this movement treat the Earth as an unlimited canvas for the

continuing patterns of human expansion, others display a more empathetic attitude. Their realizations seem to take into account the equivalence of non-human elements of the environment. It is also accompanied by a shift in philosophical anthropologies.

The distinction between man and "everything else" begins to lose its sharpness, and the opposition between culture and nature is no longer obvious. The Cartesian *res cogitans* and *res extensa* are slowly coming closer together. Ontological dualism—the division into the intentional worlds of human subjects and the objective world of material things, or for short, into society and nature (Ingold 2000: 159) - ceases to dominate the narratives. The interaction of human and non-human beings, so far considered unidirectionally, turns out to be symmetrical (or almost symmetrical). The non-human cannot remain a territory of subjugation and colonization, but demands understanding in all of its subjectivity.

The twentieth-century philosophers also criticized the domination of sight, established in tradition, especially in the epistemological aspect (Welsch 2005, 127). The world demands knowing - leading to understanding - with all the senses. Perhaps art in particular is capable of reflecting the variety of responses to this call. It seems, however, that, for example, most contemporary artistic practices in the field of nature-sound art (sound space) do not fully exhaust the existing possibilities. This is because in general it is based on recording the sounds of the environment and using them to compose one's own narratives/compositions. It is similar to photographing a landscape, treated either as an end in itself or as a starting point for further activities; in effect, we get what is already known. Even more doubts are raised by treating the environment as a sphere of artistic exploration according to the rules imposed by man. This form of hidden colonization of the environment is only another method of human self-expression, in which the protagonist who speaks becomes an actor in a directed play.

Much more ethical and at the same time more creatively promising seems to me to respect the assumptions of critical post-humanism (Bakke 2010, 338) and to introduce non-human beings into the field of art as active participants. A recognition of their subjectivity and an attempt at empathic understanding allows us to discover hitherto unrecognized aspects of art born out of human cooperation with living and inanimate nature (Bakke 2010, 357). This paves the way for the adoption of the concept in which human beings are no longer autonomous components of a humanistic ontology, but are only constituted in coexistence with many inhuman actants. Thus, the viewer gains a chance to track sets of relationships between things of all kinds, human and inhuman, without prior judgments about the roles played by various types of entities. (**insert Fig_1 here)

This work connects naturally to the PostHumanTerrain framework (Sepideh Majidi), because the non-human elements I work with – rivers, mushrooms, materials – are not aesthetic subjects, but operational co-agents. In my approach, the terrain is not the background for artistic action. It is the field that performs action. The PostHumanTerrain concept names exactly this shift: that art does not happen on the world, but with the world, and that non-human entities are not referenced but activated, not represented but allowed to operate.

One such invisible and so far undiscovered forms of non-human art is the voice of the river. Reaching it requires penetrating the mentally impenetrable surface of flowing water. Hence, the application of physics becomes necessary. There is a phenomenon known in fluid dynamics – the Kármán vortex–responsible for unsteady separation of flow of a fluid around blunt bodies (Amalia & al. 2017). Following its principle and thus exploring the physicality of depth, I transpose it into a completely new experience. Since 2016, I have been extracting and recording the voice of rivers and the visual effect of their energy. In this case, rivers are treated as the subject (author) of creative action; I am only letting them reveal themselves. With the help of strings immersed in the river current, I discover her voice, which is a representation of the power hidden within it: creative and destructive. The strings vibrate under the influence of flowing water masses, and thanks to the acoustic and/or electronic amplification, their vibrations become loud enough to recognize the timbre of individual sound sequences. I have made recordings in many places around the world. It turns out that every river sounds different. All these sounds constitute an important element of the environment and constantly shape the development of a very sensitive brain (McQuay & Joyce 2015). The vibrations of the strings placed in the river current can also be translated into visual effects - into images created by flowing water that moves the pens and organizes patterns of pigment particles. I only provide tools, but I do not interfere with the resulting pattern of lines and spots. (**insert Fig_2 here) (**insert Fig_3 here)

The recordings collected so far (<http://latentvoice.pl/>) seem to indicate that the sounds of individual rivers seem to exhibit characteristics belonging to their particular regions. For now, my research base does not allow for further development of this hypothesis. The methods of imaging sounds have also not been exhausted. Moreover, it would be interesting to be able to confront the sounds of regional rivers with the specific audiosphere of particular places through which they flow, together with the sound of speech, and as a result - the creation of a multidimensional space enabling simultaneous listening/ experiencing the vibrations of the natural and human environment. Such a juxtaposition of human and non-human activity (creativity) could constitute a new platform for non-human understanding and perhaps even a change of habitus, enhancing the importance of cooperation and interdependencies as basic survival factors. "We need reflection on the changing position of man not only in relation to other forms of life, but also artifacts and inanimate nature" (Bakke 2010: 357). As I am convinced that I have not exhausted all the possibilities of dialogue with rivers, I intend to develop the project more.

The experience gained allows me to design the extension of the research field to other beings and their creative potential. Mushrooms, in which - like in rivers - transport of fluids takes place, seem to be promising. Since there is movement, it is possible to find a form of its recording in the form of sound and image. Mushrooms, although so distant from humans in biological systematics, can also turn out to be their partners. Listening to the voices of their inner life, to the pulsating energy, is an attempt to reach their essence. These sounds can be compared, or even combined,

with the sounds extracted from beneath the human skin and recorded. (**insert Fig_4 here)(**insert Fig_5 here)

In this way, the beholder of art will discover the dark space of subcutaneous connections between entangled hyphae (threads, fibers?), going beyond the biological nature of natural beings. Such an experience of community/universality of non-obvious manifestations of life knocks the man out of the rut of domination and indicates his equal place in nature.

This confirms that things become what they are and become meaningful only in and through the network of relationships. It is related to the way of thinking about agency, not as the sole capacity of human beings (conscious, reflective and intentional actors), but all participants in the environment. Here, I see a crack that allows us to cross the rigid boundaries of human reality and perceive the *umwelten* of earthly beings.

The cultivation of necessary research material – mushrooms/mycelium - can also be used to create living objects whose final form, as dependent on biological intentions, cannot be predicted. In this case, the role of the human author is only to choose the medium/method by which the nonhuman co-author can demonstrate his discrete reality. The moment when a traditional artist gives up his autonomy is the emergence of a new form of symbolic practice, producing a new, symbolically structured social environment. Works created in the broadly understood field of humanity (as a total set of systems of the human, cultural, technological and biological species), whose materials and technologies are an interspecies cooperation, show a deeper connection with the biological nature of existence. The symbiotic artist (Margulis 1998) creates work whose temporal and spatial boundaries cannot be defined. Such dispersed authorship meets the requirements of the departure from the anthropocentric perspective postulated in critical posthumanism. My artistic activity in recent years is specific and non-canonical, because it refers to the biogenic elements of the Earth. As a part of it, I would like to verify the current procedures of cooperation with non-human beings and conduct research (theoretical and practical-artistic) on nature and its overhuman perspectives. The transformation of actors into authors irreversibly changes the perspective of the spectacle participant, which is (still!) the terrestrial environment. In order to understand the operation of society, and hence to influence it, we should perceive of all its members as "real and cooperating wholes made up of both humans and nonhumans" (Olsen 2013, 14). In this case, art becomes a kind of interface connecting earthly beings. "Bio art is such a subversive, activist, penetrating activity of a critical look at what is - without choking on the spectacular effects technological" (Grabowska 2016).

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Bio

Jarek Lustych is a visual, audio, and multimedia artist, and a PhD student at the Doctoral School of Humanities and Art of UMCS (Lublin, Poland). His works refer to social and political problems and post-humanist theories. Since 2000, he has been creating projects that take into account the natural components of the environment, which then become co-authors of the works or their active participants. He uses various media, including recycled materials, but tries not to produce new objects. He also draws attention to unnoticed aspects of the environment. His projects have been implemented in collaboration with such institutions as the Pilar Juncosa & Joan Miró Foundation (2005, Palma de Mallorca), Künstlerhaus Villa Waldberta (2017, Munich), Luxlakes A4 Art Museum (2019, Chengdu, China) and the Foksal gallery (2021, Warsaw).